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Does Jaina Epistemology Indicate a Many-Valued Logic

Dr. Sabeena P S¹

Abstract

This paper attempts to reconsider the relationship between rationality and consistency and discusses about the logical basis of many valued logic. The ontological component of the anekānta vāda thesis proceeds via its logical corollary of a seven-step formulation, sapta-bhaṅgī, within a form of dialectical reasoning or, better, conditioned predication, called syad vāda, (semantics of possibilities). This paper is to offer a new interpretation of syad vada with reference to many valued logic, by means of it try to draw out some of its philosophical implications.

Keywords: *anekāntavāda, syad vāda, doctrine of relativity, classical logic, many valued logic.*

Jaina Anekanta Vada in The Context of Syad Vada

Anekāntavāda is the central philosophy of Jainism. A distinctive Jain contribution to Indian philosophy, it speaks about three teachings called the Jain 'doctrines of relativity'. The first doctrine is *anekāntavāda*, teaches that reality is irreducibly complex, or *anekānta* (literally 'non-one-sided'). No entity can be reduced to a single characteristic or concept. To exist is to be multi-faceted. The second doctrine is *Nayavāda*, it is the doctrine of perspectives, is a logical implication of *anekāntavāda*: a claim about the nature of knowledge. Given the complexity of reality that *anekāntavāda* posits,

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an entity may be known from a variety of *nayas*, or perspectives, that correspond to its many facets. The third doctrine is *syādvāda*, the doctrine of conditional predication, asserts that the truth of a claim is dependent upon the perspective from which it is made. A claim can be true, in one sense or from one perspective (the technical meaning of the Sanskrit verb 'syād' in a Jain context), false from another perspective, both true and false from another, have an inexpressible truth-value from yet another, and so on (Long). For example,

- 1) A claim is, in one sense, true.
- 2) A claim is, in another sense, false.
- 3) A claims is, in another sense, both true and false.
- 4) The truth of a claim is, in another sense, inexpressible.
- 5) A claim is, in another sense, both true and its truth is inexpressible.
- 6) A claim is, in another sense, both false and its truth inexpressible.
- 7) A claim is, in another sense, both true and false and its truth is inexpressible

The method of honestly accepting and reconciling the apparently contradictory attributes in a thing from different standpoints is called *syad vada* or *anekantavada*. Yet another example is, a woman, we accept seemingly different attributes – that is, we call her a mother, daughter, aunt, daughter-in-law, mother – in – law etc, because it is a different relation with respect to the standpoint of different persons which she familiarizes. Similarly, one accepts apparently opposite attributes viz; permanence and impermanence etc. in a thing, say a pot, because one reconciles them with one another from different standpoints (Matilal 55). Or in other way, a well-known parable is presented of an elephant and five blind-folded men who are explaining elephant with their understanding. each men touches different parts of the elephant and each reports that the elephant is whatever part of the animal each happensto be feeling: trunk, legs, ear-flaps, tail, torso (i.e. the particular characteristic). In other words, each came up with a partial truth as none could feel the animal in its magnificentfullness or conjure up a 3 - dimensional image from all angles as those blessed with vision are able to, most often (Matilal

58). (ideas adopted from Prof. B K Matilal)

The ontological component of the *anekāntavāda* thesis proceeds via its logical corollary of a seven-step formulation, *sapta-bhaṅgī*, within a form of dialectical reasoning or, better, conditioned predication, called *syadvāda*, (semantics of possibilities). Technical details aside, this is what it looks like (adopted from Matilal, 1981): (Adopt operator S, *Syāt*: somehow or from a particular point of view).

- (1) *Syād asti* (somehow, i.e., from some particular point of view, a thing may besaid to exist as itself).
- (2) *Syād nāsti* (somehow, from another point of view, the thing does not exist as itself, but possibly as something else).
- (3) *Syād asti nāsti* (taking both angles of (1) and (2) together, there is affirmation of existence as itself from one point of view and of non-existence of itself from another).
- (4) *Syād avaktavya* (despite both views being present, somehow the thing is indescribable).
- (5) *Syād asti avaktavya* (a combination of the first and the fourth forms of predication; somehow the thing is itself and still indescribable or indeterminate).
- (6) *Syād nāsti avaktavya* (a combination of the second and the fourth forms; somehow there is non-existence of itself and is still indescribable or indeterminate).
- (7) *Syād asti nāsti avaktavya* (a combination of the first, second and fourth forms of judgment; somehow the thing is existent as itself, is non-existent as itself, and yet is describable or indeterminate).

Many Valued Logic

Syad vada tries to explain the ontological experiencing of an incident, it point toward the multiple faceted aspect of the corresponding fact. So, let's see what the multifaceted concepts of logic is. Many valued logics are non-classical logic. They differ from classical logic by the fundamental fact that they do not restrict the number of truth values to only two, they allow for a larger set of truth degrees.

Classical logic is a kind of logic based on the principle that each assertion has a truth value of either 'true' or 'false', but not both. Binary system is based on classic bivalent logic (Wiredu). The core principle of bivalent logic is The Law of Excluded Middle, $p \vee \sim p$, and The Principle of Contradiction $\sim (p \vee \sim p)$. The truth table of Law of Excluded Middle is:

A	$A \vee \sim A$
T	T
F	T

Here, there is no middle ground in between truth and falsity, hence it is called excludedmiddle. In the Law of Excluded Middle, whatever the values of the variable A, such aseither true or false, the resultant value of Law of Excluded Middle will be true. The truth table of the Principle of Contradiction is:

A	$\sim(A \vee \sim A)$
T	F
F	F

In Principle of contradiction, if the variable A carries the value true or false, the resultant principle of contradiction will be false. These are the core principles of bivalent logic.

When we credit truth or falsity as the two possible values for a given proposition we also credit numerical values for those propositions, if it is true 1 and 0 if it is false. Butin the case of vague sentences could not be given a definite value in classical logic and hence vagueness presents a challenge to classical logic; for example, a sentence containing vague predicates cannot be given a definite value and therefore, such sentences cannot be effectively represented in classical logic.

It was Aristotle, who first questioned the viability of the Principle of Excluded Middle, in Chapter IX of *De Interpretatione*, he comes up with the timely honored sentence “*There will be a sea*

battle tomorrow”, which cannot be evaluated from the standard correspondence intuitions on truth and falsity. But his isolated remark was not potent. Aristotelian tradition picked it up, which resulted in the creation of a path breaking discovery in the field of logic. It was the Polish logician and philosopher JanLukasiewicz who initiated the trend in 1920 by creating systems of many-valued logic using a third value, “possible” to deal with Aristotle’s paradox of the sea of battle (Schumann and Florentin Smarandache). Meanwhile in 1921 Emile E. Post, an American mathematician, also introduced the formulation of additional truth degrees with $n \geq 2$, where n represent the truth values. But the famous contemporary logician Graham Priest also speak about the phenomenon of truth value glut and truthvalue gap.

In a sense the philosophical motivation for Many Valued Logic originates fundamentally from two phenomena in logic called truth value glut and truth value gap. Truth value glut, is when we come across in ordinary language sentences, where the sentence is forced to have both truth and falsity, and truth value gap indicates a linguistic phenomenon, where the sentence under consideration is neither true nor false. For example, consider the sentence ‘*This sentence is false*’, imagine that it is true, then what it says is that it is false, hence it is false. Suppose on the other hand, that it is false, since it says that it is false, it becomes true. In either case the value we must obtain seems to question the inconsistency of the Law of Excluded Middle. All of Russell’s paradoxes are instances of truth value glut: consider the famous case of set of all those sets, which are not members of themselves. Examples of truth value gap is,

Old paradoxes like the Sorites (heap) or the falakros (bald man). In the case of the Sorites, the paradox is as follows: (i) One grain of sand is not a heap of sand. (ii) Adding one grain of sand to a collection of sand that is not a heap does not convert it into a heap. Therefore, (iii) One grain of sand will never go to make a heap of sand, no matter how many grains of sand are added to it. Thus, the true premise (i) provides a false conclusion (iii) via a sequence of inferences using (ii). A solution that we can hope for within the purview of Many Valued Logic would be one that permits a graded notion of inference, often called fuzzy logic.

Yet another example for truth values gap is, A man with one hair on his head is bald; If a man with 1 hair on his head is bald then a man with un2 is.

- If a man with 2 hairs on his head is bald then a man with 3 is.
- If a man with 9,999 hairs on his head is bald then a man with 10,000 is
- Therefore, a man with 10,000 hairs on his head is bald (Hyde 290).

Interestingly, both these paradoxes date back at least to 4th century BC. The key to the solution to these paradoxes seem to lie in multivaluedness or fuzzy logic. I have already pointed out that, Lukasiewicz introduced third value logic. He introduced a third value, added to 'true' and 'false' that he called 'possible' or 'undetermined', symbolically denoted by $\frac{1}{2}$, 0 and 1 being used as usual to denote falsity and truth. More light can be thrown on the meaning of the third truth-value from the following passage redrafted from Lukasiewicz: The proposition 'I shall be in London at noon on 29 December of next year', can be neither true nor false on the basis of present time. The above sentence if it were to be true, I should be in London the next year, thereby making it to be a necessary proposition, which is contradictory to the assumption. If it were false, on the other hand, my future presence in London would have to be impossible, which is also contradictory to the assumption (Baylis). Therefore, when we analyse the proposition considered at the moment, it is neither true nor false and must possess a third value, different from '0' or falsity and '1' or truth. This value can be designated by ' $\frac{1}{2}$ '. It corresponds 'the possible', and joins 'the true' and 'the false' as a 'third value'.

Attribution of Mathematical Values

The classical two – valued logic can be extended into n-valued logics. If the cardinal value is n, then the logic is called n- valued. Finitely many valued logic asserts that the cardinal value is finite otherwise it is infinite many valued logic. During 1930s several n – valued logics were developed. The set T_n of truth values of n – valued logic is thus defined as -

$$T_n = \{0 = 1/n-1, 2/n-1, 3/n-1, \dots, n-2/n-1, n-1/n-1 = 1\} \text{ Hence}$$

Valued logic can be defined as

$$T_7 = \{0 = 0/7-1, 1/7-1, 2/7-1, 3/7-1, 4/7-1, 5/7-1, 6/7-1 = 1\}$$

These values can be interpreted as degrees of truth. Or previously it is pointed out that fuzzy logic. The first series of n – valued logics for which was proposed by Lukasiewicz in the early 1930’s as a generalization of his three – valued logic. For example, suppose a dog is sick, as is every day experience, we have the following possibilities:

1. The Dog is well - Is (True - 1)
2. The Dog is not well - Is not (False - 0)
3. The Dog is well as well as not well - Is and Is not (True & False - 2/6)
4. The Dog’s condition is inexpressible as nothing can be said definitely - Is inexpressible (Indeterminant - 3/6)
5. The Dog is well but nothing can be said or is inexpressible - Is and is inexpressible (True & Indeterminant - 5/6)
6. The Dog is unwell but nothing can be said or is inexpressible - Is not and is inexpressible (False & Indeterminant - 1/6)
7. The Dog is well as well as unwell at the same time inexpressible as nothing can be said - Is and Is not and is Inexpressible (True, False & Indeterminant - 4/6).

If we follow Luksiewicz logic, we could write Jaina Logic in the following way, such as

Assigning logical numerical values to the seven fold judgment of Jaina Logic we get,

F	F&I	T&F	I	T,F&I	T&I	T
0	1/6	2/6	3/6	4/6	5/6	1

Here, indeterminate value or indescribable is 3/6 or ½ (Malathi)

Conclusion

To conclude, we have seen that, in Jainism, a particular object can be viewed from many dimensions, and each dimension has its own views. The term “*anekanta*” implies the ontological nature of reality, in which it means each and every object possesses infinite aspects and attitudes. We have seen that in Jaina seven valued logic, all the truth values are understood to be combinations in some way or another of two classical values. Or in other words, Jain seven

valued logic speaks only basically three values such as truth, false and indescribable. Opinion of Lukasiewicz is that ‘If third value is introduced into logic, its very foundations itself will change. Graham Priest called it as truthvalue glut, that is, a sentence carrying the value of true and false together. Here it is 2/6 according to the principle of Lukasiewicz. At any rate, we have seen, as promised, the application of contemporary logical techniques to historical theories in Indian logic can be just as fruitful as their application to historical theories in European knowledge.

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